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RE: Morten Konggard Schou

IT
00:00.000 --> 00:10.960

Let's get started. Thank you for taking the time out of your day to take this interview.

IT
00:10.960 --> 00:19.020

How are students currently collaborating and sharing coding exercises for the IMPR course?

RE
00:19.020 --> 00:27.980

They collaborate with the group exercises where they are asked to work on the exercises

RE
00:27.980 --> 00:36.700

in their group rooms, so the physical structure of the group room is quite important for that.

RE
00:36.700 --> 00:43.220

They are encouraged to discuss the exercise together before they start working on ideas

RE
00:43.220 --> 00:54.620

for figuring out how to solve the exercise. I know some of the students also code together.

RE
00:54.620 --> 01:01.960

I encourage that each student does their own coding, but at least writing it down because

RE
01:01.960 --> 01:09.080

that kind of practice is beneficial even if you do it together. But some students just

RE
01:09.080 --> 01:19.740

look at the common screen where they code, like one person is typing and they're discussing.

RE
01:19.740 --> 01:34.460

They kind of use this shared coding feature in CLION, but some other students code on each other, like their own computer.

IT

01:34.460 --> 01:40.580

How is exercise feedback handled for both students and lecturers?

RE

01:40.580 --> 01:55.440

The exercise feedback, we're using a pull request in GitHub. For assignments where they

RE

01:55.440 --> 02:06.660

get feedback, they use GitHub Classroom to make a fork of a repository that has the exercise

RE

02:06.660 --> 02:16.660

questions and then they make a push to their own repository with the answer and then there

RE

02:16.660 --> 02:23.500

is an automatic feedback pull request where we can look through the changes that they've

RE

02:23.500 --> 02:34.780

made and give both a general comment and specific comments to the lines in the code.

IT

02:34.780 --> 02:39.220

What about specifically in exercise sessions, the one after lectures?

RE

02:39.220 --> 02:48.540

There the feedback is interactive in the sense that we have me, the lecturer, and then four

RE

02:48.540 --> 02:57.740

teaching assistants that walk around and interact with the students and discuss the exercises

RE

02:57.740 --> 03:05.580

and mainly maybe help with the current issues that the students are facing, but of course

RE

03:05.580 --> 03:12.700

also giving feedback on partial solutions and so on.

IT

03:12.700 --> 03:20.100

How do these current tools and methods fall short in facilitating co-sharing or collaboration

IT

03:20.100 --> 03:23.980

if they do?

RE

03:23.980 --> 03:33.980

I think they work pretty well. I haven't really identified specific issues. So I guess the

RE

03:33.980 --> 03:41.860

GitHub Classroom, there's some practical issues that is a bit cumbersome to distribute the

RE

03:41.860 --> 03:50.060

assignments between the teaching assistants and me. But that's more like a technical issue

RE

03:50.060 --> 03:56.460

with interfacing with GitHub Classroom is a bit cumbersome. But other than that, I think

RE

03:56.460 --> 04:03.500

using pull requests for assignment feedback is good because it's similar to how you would

RE

04:03.500 --> 04:10.420

get feedback in your first job, for example, as a junior programmer. You typically get

RE

04:10.420 --> 04:16.460

feedback through pull requests and it can also be useful for students to know about

RE

04:16.460 --> 04:22.460

pull requests for their project work. So it can be a way of structuring the code collaboration

RE

04:22.460 --> 04:32.140

even. So I think that that is working pretty well. Maybe one thing that's not so good is

RE

04:32.140 --> 04:39.980

that it takes a lot of time to give detailed feedback. But that's more like a resource

RE

04:39.980 --> 04:46.620

issue that there's only so much time allocated for teaching and we should try to not exceed

RE

04:46.620 --> 04:58.300

that. For the exercise sessions, what it's not supposed to... You asked about code collaboration.

IT

04:58.300 --> 05:03.860

If there are any areas of improvement you see for this right now, as we also know because

IT

05:03.860 --> 05:08.900

we have done the course, code collaboration is mainly just like a normal pair program

IT

05:08.900 --> 05:22.260

but with a screen. So somewhat MOB programming.

RE

Yeah, true. I don't think that more code sharing

RE

05:22.260 --> 05:32.380

would necessarily be beneficial. I think because I think being able to discuss the issues together

RE

05:32.380 --> 05:41.140

and then a program on your own is probably the most effective way of learning. And then

RE

05:41.140 --> 05:49.580

the option for having this common screen is useful for some students. I don't know what

RE

05:49.580 --> 05:56.300

would be the improvement to be honest.

IT

We've spoken with some of the students from your

IT

05:56.300 --> 06:00.980

course from last semester, which we are also part of. And many of them agree with the fact

IT

06:00.980 --> 06:05.500

that the learning curve for new coders is somewhat steep since they both have to learn

IT

06:05.500 --> 06:13.180

Git and C and also some other tools, CLion, VS Code, whatever IDE they want to use. And

IT

06:13.180 --> 06:17.300

since they have to be learned simultaneously, it is somewhat of a steep learning curve and

IT

06:17.300 --> 06:25.220

hard. Do you see any value in adopting a more sequential learning approach where students

IT

06:25.220 --> 06:31.700

first learn coding in C before learning these extra tools for example Git? And if so,

IT

06:31.700 --> 06:40.060

how might this positively impact their learning experience?

RE

06:40.060 --> 06:48.140

Yeah, it's a long one. So I can maybe answer it because we've only been using this setup for two years. So previously we

RE

06:48.140 --> 06:54.740

didn't use an IDE like CLion and we didn't use Git. The course with the previous teacher

RE

06:54.740 --> 07:09.900

used just plain terminal GCC where you write, you directly compile the file in the terminal.

RE

07:09.900 --> 07:18.100

That is also a tool that you need to learn to use. And part of the motivation for doing

RE

07:18.100 --> 07:24.640

it this way is that you basically only need CLion and you can get that free and then you

RE

07:24.640 --> 07:32.400

have a visual GUI and then a tool that can do everything. So the idea was that you get

RE

07:32.400 --> 07:38.240

started with coding faster than if you have to learn. For example, there's a lot of people

RE

07:38.240 --> 07:45.140

on Windows, they have to download and make this terminal work, which is not trivial at

RE

07:45.140 --> 07:52.440

all when you need this Linux-like terminal. And then installing the compiler, figure out

RE

07:52.440 --> 07:59.280

how to work with the compiler, figure out how to work with C source files without any

RE

07:59.280 --> 08:06.080

IDE help. There's some value in knowing that it's just files and text, there's nothing

RE

08:06.080 --> 08:16.800

fancy in there. But the guy who was there last time and then me, we think that it's

RE

08:16.800 --> 08:23.400

better to just start programming and then having one tool that can also do Git, can

RE

08:23.400 --> 08:37.600

also do compilation and is probably faster at getting started. So yes, there's also another

RE

08:37.600 --> 08:44.920

reason that for feedback, having access to GitHub classroom and the pull requests, I think

RE

08:44.920 --> 08:52.760

makes the process easier compared to having some external or separate assignment hand

RE

08:52.760 --> 08:59.720

in tool where they hand in a source file and they have to be downloaded and distributed

RE

08:59.720 --> 09:10.760

and somehow given feedback to. There was some system earlier that was more or less handmade.

IT

09:10.760 --> 09:16.440

You mentioned that the setup is quite important as each setup and you started coding, would

IT

09:16.440 --> 09:22.560

it be beneficial to have some tool that then instead was a web platform and then there

IT

09:22.560 --> 09:30.160

was no setup basically installed on server and just start coding.

RE

09:30.160 --> 09:40.360

So I think there could be some idea that you can flatten the learning curve by being able to start programming in

RE

09:40.360 --> 09:51.160

C without any setup. Then the question is at what point do you transition to a more

RE

09:51.160 --> 09:57.380

like realistic setup where you have the tools that you would use for normal programming

RE

09:57.380 --> 10:06.560

because you also need to use that in the project at some point during the semester. But yeah,

RE

10:06.560 --> 10:20.400

I guess there's a point in that you could get started even easier with a web-based tool.

RE

10:20.400 --> 10:25.600

The way the course is structured currently is that the first entire lecture is only for

RE

10:25.600 --> 10:33.080

getting started and setting up tools and trying out a dummy program essentially and then we start

RE

10:33.080 --> 10:42.180

programming in the next session. So with that different setup I guess we could move

RE

10:42.180 --> 10:49.740

that introduction to C a bit earlier but then you would have to find some point where

RE

10:49.740 --> 10:58.700

you learn to use the real tool.

IT

10:58.700 --> 11:12.440

Are there any other challenges within the IMPR course that you see could be addressed by a web-based collaborative coding tool?

RE

11:12.440 --> 11:21.520

So I've been thinking about automating feedback in some way. I think the challenge is that

RE

11:21.520 --> 11:27.720

the type of feedback you need to give especially early on in the course is more qualitative

RE

11:27.720 --> 11:34.500

than like quantitative automating that you cannot just run some automated tests and see

RE

11:34.500 --> 11:42.860

if the students did it correctly because the students that need good feedback, well they

RE

11:42.860 --> 11:47.660

don't necessarily write code that compiles even or makes any kind of sense but you have

RE

11:47.660 --> 11:54.540

to try to figure out what is the correct like what is the best way of explaining to them

RE

11:54.540 --> 12:00.360

like the thing they need to understand next to be able to improve and that is not easy

RE

12:00.360 --> 12:11.040

to automated. Maybe towards maybe for the exercises automated like checking if the solution is

RE

12:11.040 --> 12:19.880

correct could work but then yeah there's also the if it should be a balance because they

RE

12:19.880 --> 12:27.140

should also know about the qualitative parts like code style and having a nice structure

RE

12:27.140 --> 12:35.620

of the code not just making code that's correct. So there could be some automated feedback

RE

12:35.620 --> 12:42.300

I think would be valuable in the course in general it could also I know that you can

RE

12:42.300 --> 13:02.880

also do this in GitHub with GitHub actions and this classroom does allow for some automated testing of the code.

IT

So your experience with GitHub classroom as a sort of coding sharing

IT

13:02.880 --> 13:10.560

and storage of these exercises or assignments has that had a good impact on the teaching

IT

13:10.560 --> 13:14.980

of the course or what impact did it have on the quality and efficiency of the teaching

IT

13:14.980 --> 13:20.520

rather?

RE

13:20.520 --> 13:27.780

I think for the exercises and the assignments it's been working really well that there is kind of the template with the formulation of the exercises and so on that

RE

13:27.780 --> 13:36.220

and some like starter code that the students can start up from and we have that as a repository

RE

13:36.220 --> 13:43.320

and I can improve that gradually and then reuse for the next year it was like if there's

RE

13:43.320 --> 13:50.000

some typos I fixed or other things that I don't need to do the all the work to set it

RE

13:50.000 --> 13:57.000

up every time and then having a starter code makes it easier to just get started for example

RE

13:57.000 --> 14:04.240

the CMake setup is not something that's necessary at least in the beginning only later on in

RE

14:04.240 --> 14:11.140

the course when it starts to be useful for the project work then I try to make it a more

RE

14:11.140 --> 14:17.820

important part of the exercises to know about it but having the starter code I think is

RE

14:17.820 --> 14:26.500

really important and I also use the GitHub classroom feature for the like during the

RE

14:26.500 --> 14:36.520

lectures where there is some yeah like yeah assignments or small exercises during the

RE

14:36.520 --> 14:44.480

lecture where they get the code and then I also upload the solutions to the exercises

RE

14:44.480 --> 14:50.720

and I also do live coding and I have like the starter code in the repository and they

RE

14:50.720 --> 14:55.560

can tag along and then I also would like to have the like upload the final code I didn't

RE

14:55.620 --> 15:01.660

after the lecture but the way the classroom works is that there when you when the student

RE

15:01.660 --> 15:09.060

forks the repository then it's kind of fixed and I cannot update the version they're looking at

RE

15:09.060 --> 15:17.980

because they fork the version that's currently there so that meant it was a bit tricky to both

RE

15:17.980 --> 15:26.720

let them start working on the like on the first exercise and maybe follow along with the live

RE

15:26.720 --> 15:32.440

coding and also give them the the final version so sometimes I uploaded that as a as a plain C

RE

15:32.440 --> 15:39.680

file in Moodle but I realized towards the end of the course that it's possible to to fix this by

RE

15:39.680 --> 15:47.440

having an empty file that I do the live coding in and then having the intended solution and I'm

RE

15:47.440 --> 15:56.300

working forward towards in a separate file and have that in the repository and yeah but there

RE

15:56.300 --> 16:05.420

was that specific challenge that you cannot update it later on easily and you make 200

RE

16:05.420 --> 16:13.860

repositories for each year each update or each year base repository you make and all the students

RE

16:13.860 --> 16:24.600

make and make new repositories and there's some overhead in that in each of these but I yeah you

RE

16:24.600 --> 16:30.400

asked if there was something I needed for like I was missing

IT

it was rather what was the impact

IT

16:30.400 --> 16:37.680

impact on your teaching?

RE

I think I did the first impact that I could yeah easily share

RE

16:38.620 --> 16:45.660

code in a way that they could start working like so once they figured out how to pull the correct

RE

16:45.660 --> 16:52.500

repository then they could easily get it on there in the IDE and didn't have to worry about where

RE

16:52.500 --> 16:58.100

files are located on the computer which yeah apparently is something that kids these days just

RE

16:58.100 --> 17:08.560

don't know

IT

If we are looking at a sort of like a co-collaboration web-based tool maybe to replace

IT

17:08.560 --> 17:13.600

Github Classroom what specific features are then needed to support like an effective collaboration

IT

17:13.600 --> 17:19.920

between the students and also between the lecturer because I mean you mentioned

IT

17:19.920 --> 17:26.000

live coding how could that be improved maybe if there's also a sort of collaboration between

IT

17:26.000 --> 17:31.620

the lecturer and the students yeah I remember we could raise our hand and say and

IT

17:31.620 --> 17:39.820

that was somewhat hard it's at line character ...

RE

yeah so yeah there was something I

RE

17:39.820 --> 17:46.820

intended to do that didn't really work out that was the like after air like one of these small

RE

17:46.820 --> 17:55.300

exercises within a lecture I wanted to show solutions but the student answers and comment

RE

17:55.300 --> 18:07.040

on those but the overhead of of a receiving these answers and figure out which which one to show and

RE

18:07.040 --> 18:16.040

make that working with a over email was it didn't really work out because that they also the course

RE

18:16.040 --> 18:21.600

needed to kind of continue so at least I didn't find a good solution for that with that when you

RE

18:21.600 --> 18:29.300

have a big auditorium was yeah with a lot of students waiting so maybe a tool could make it

RE

18:29.300 --> 18:36.460

easier for a student to say I would like to share yeah my solution and then I could just click a

RE

18:36.460 --> 18:47.020

button and and then open it on my screen and and they come on the solution yeah so that was at

RE

18:47.020 --> 18:54.960

least during the lecture I think that was an issue

IT

18:54.960 --> 18:58.760

Outside of the lecture are there any specific features that are needed to support like an effective collaboration and also communication

IT

18:58.760 --> 19:09.680

just among students from your view?

RE

19:09.680 --> 19:16.740

I think it's been useful for some students to be able to like code together so they don't all right type all the characters but I'm not convinced if it's

RE

19:16.740 --> 19:33.980

necessary for effective learning but it seems to be something that you prefer yeah, I think yeah

RE

19:33.980 --> 19:40.080

I think that's maybe I already mentioned it this but there should also be some way of transitioning

RE

19:40.080 --> 19:47.160

to a more realistic setup like if like maybe downloading the the project and being able to

RE

19:47.160 --> 19:57.200

open it in an editor somehow so this is yeah not so much based on my experience as a teacher but

RE

19:57.200 --> 20:05.740

more as a user of these for example like code Academy or whatever that existing online frameworks

RE

20:05.740 --> 20:13.380

for learning a specific programming language or with language and that environment is quite

RE

20:13.380 --> 20:20.660

different from what you'll be using in a real project and then as a teacher here I think that

RE

20:20.660 --> 20:29.560

is important that you also learn the necessary tools and knowledge to actually develop actual

RE + IT

20:29.560 --> 20:45.840

code on your computer okay yeah it's transitioning yes yeah that is yeah somehow is at least if the

RE

20:45.840 --> 20:51.380

intention is to lower the learning curve and it's mostly for that beginning of the first half of the

RE

20:51.380 --> 21:01.200

course and it can transition out of maybe it can still be used for like if it has automated testing

RE

21:01.200 --> 21:11.660

it can be useful like this kind of recap or quick exercises yeah yeah my I'm also curious how like

RE

21:11.660 --> 21:18.500

how it would work for projects with multiple files and like more complex projects so that's why I'm

RE

21:18.500 --> 21:36.320

thinking that it's probably mostly useful for the kind of simple programs you would do in the beginning yeah yeah

IT

If we backtrack to collaboration currently when asking for help for students in the

IT

21:37.280 --> 21:47.120

exercise section of the lectures the current help request system is somewhat basic it's still

IT

21:47.120 --> 21:52.160

outside the door or a chair or something. Do you think it would be a helpful to have a sort of

IT

21:52.160 --> 22:02.280

system live chat in this web-based platform?

RE

I think so yeah I think yeah being able to request

RE

22:02.280 --> 22:11.200

help and somehow indicate like where you're located and then also for the teacher the TA to

RE

22:11.200 --> 22:17.280

indicate an acknowledgement so that we know okay someone has taken care of this yeah that would be

RE

22:17.280 --> 22:30.240

beneficial. I think other teachers have been using it teams room like teams group or discord

IT

22:30.240 --> 22:37.320

but that is lacking acknowledgement

RE

I haven't tried it. I don't know much about discord

RE

22:37.320 --> 22:45.920

but I think the team's room would be useful I think I would use that next time yeah

RE

22:45.920 --> 22:55.360
if I don't have other ideas.

IT

if we are talking about this web-based platform again for coding

IT

22:55.360 --> 23:00.680
how should it accommodate different learning styles and also skill levels to ensure that

IT

23:00.680 --> 23:07.280
beginners actively benefit from collaboration and not just rely on their more skilled group members

RE

23:07.280 --> 23:16.160
yeah well I don't know if I can answer the how, I guess that is your job, but it's definitely

RE

23:16.160 --> 23:22.480
true that it should accommodate very different levels and that at least it should accommodate

RE

23:22.480 --> 23:30.440
the beginner skill levels, because that's the main issue. I think that's the students that

RE

23:30.440 --> 23:40.200
there are students that have absolutely no background in programming or and yeah they

RE

23:40.200 --> 23:50.680
they struggle with the learning curve in the beginning yeah and yeah I think that they should

RE

23:50.680 --> 23:59.200
be forced to do programming alone not isolated but like on their own computer at least because

RE

23:59.880 --> 24:09.840
at least from my experience you learn mostly by trying I think that's also another point

RE

24:09.840 --> 24:17.800

this is not something I'm an expert in but I think that some students will be a bit like

RE

24:17.800 --> 24:27.080

scared of showing what they have tried if they are unsure whether it's correct and I think getting

RE

24:27.080 --> 24:38.680

over that hurdle of like being able to to show your wrong program to the teacher is an important

RE

24:38.680 --> 24:46.600

thing because yeah well you are going to fail a lot when your program ends and I think for some

RE

24:46.600 --> 24:52.360

for some students it that's a that's a new thing and something they need to get used to yeah and

RE

24:52.760 --> 25:02.200

if they don't like learn to get out of the comfort zone of only showing stuff that's correct then

RE

25:02.200 --> 25:09.320

they will have a hard time and I don't know how to solve this but if it can solve that that's

RE

25:09.320 --> 25:20.240

a benefit.

IT

Can you foresee any challenges or concerns with this online web-based

IT

25:20.240 --> 25:35.200

platform and implementing it?

RE

so I think it's a big project to do I know so I had there was a

RE

25:35.200 --> 25:46.520

similar project last year on the seventh semester yeah well he has some similar ideas and I think

RE

25:46.520 --> 25:54.800

they got almost all the way with something that could run code and give feedback based on tests

RE

25:54.800 --> 26:02.480

and so I think the scope is probably going to be challenging and that they like almost completed

[Unrelated speech]

RE

26:02.480 --> 26:16.040

it I don't know if you've talked with this group but

IT

I think we've seen that paper yeah

RE

26:16.040 --> 26:36.920

what would be concerns I think I've expressed some of the concerns yeah yeah

[Unrelated speech ends]

IT

I think we've discussed them

IT

26:36.920 --> 26:47.000

so as you also mentioned the previous professor he has previously also created and

IT

26:47.000 --> 26:51.000

used the tool for sharing exercise during his time as lecturer on the IMPR course. I'm not sure if you

IT

26:51.000 --> 26:56.120

know this. if you do were there any issues with this since you did not include it in your teaching

IT

26:56.120 --> 27:15.960

for IMPR. He has a sort of like a web-based where you see all lectures the slides and all exercises

RE

27:15.960 --> 27:25.600

I think we use this as a extra preference as an extra I think in the course page there's a link to this these slides and the exercises are also a lot of them are his

RE

27:25.600 --> 27:35.640

exercises yeah so we just decided to move it to github so it was on a single platform I think

RE

27:35.640 --> 27:46.680

there's still some links to to his slides and exercises yeah so I don't have the source code

RE

27:46.680 --> 27:55.320

so for updating the content that would be... I could probably ask him up okay yeah yeah I think it was

RE

27:55.320 --> 28:01.120

developed back when we didn't have flip classroom. So it was I think there's more content

RE

28:01.120 --> 28:08.480

on these online slides then what I cover in a in the auditorium because they we now are using

RE

28:08.480 --> 28:15.520

flipped classroom but there's bit later videos you watch at home and then the auditorium session is

RE

28:15.520 --> 28:26.880

mostly live coding yeah

IT

With creating this web-based program it is important that it is

IT

28:26.880 --> 28:34.800

effective. How would you test the usability of the tool and measure if it's effective or not?

IT

28:34.800 --> 28:50.400

I know, big question.

RE

Effective I guess I guess hmm so what yeah what would be the parameters

RE

28:50.400 --> 28:55.640

for measuring effectiveness yeah I guess I mean for my part it should be easy to use and I shouldn't

RE

28:55.640 --> 29:03.440

have to spend a lot of time on setting up the assignment and for example this automated

RE

29:03.440 --> 29:09.520

testing it you know that's a nice thing but I would have to do a lot of test cases to show

RE

29:09.520 --> 29:18.640

that's correct so making that easy and also easy for me to test that when 200 students or 170 students

RE

29:18.640 --> 29:24.760

start using it then it's actually gonna work the first day yeah yeah that is the next question

IT

29:24.760 --> 29:30.960

how would you design a sort of pilot program to test that it is actually functional and effective for

IT

29:30.960 --> 29:40.320

a whole classroom and also for the IMPR course - a sort of test of the effectiveness in the real

IT

29:40.320 --> 29:49.160

classroom setting and not just individually but as a yeah full-on program hmm

RE

I mean if it's a

RE

29:49.160 --> 29:57.040

pilot I guess I wouldn't try to scale it as much but maybe have a single group test it out yeah

RE

29:57.040 --> 30:12.760

like a few students

IT

how would you assess how you assess student collaboration and

IT

30:12.760 --> 30:22.840

engagement from the use of this tool and the changes in those?

RE

it sounds like it it's a lot

RE

30:22.840 --> 30:32.880

question that you guys should answer, but would I want to assess what collaboration and

RE

30:32.880 --> 30:44.200

engagement yeah well I guess I would measure how much they use it and how they I don't know I guess

RE

30:44.200 --> 30:50.840

I don't know if I would necessarily assess it during the course if you want to assess it from

RE

30:50.840 --> 30:59.360

like after having developed the tool you will probably do some qualitative like the

RE

30:59.360 --> 31:10.600

experiment where you take a group of students that as if they were starting the

RE

31:10.600 --> 31:18.480

course or should try to learn this and see if they like how they work on exercises in this

RE

31:19.200 --> 31:29.280

tool

IT

okay lastly what factors is needed to be considered to ensure that the tool is sustainable

IT

31:29.280 --> 31:35.760

for a long period of time this includes for example updates to the course material additional

IT

31:35.760 --> 31:43.480

support and an adaption to needs a change it changes in the occasional needs so if they

IT

31:43.480 --> 31:49.040

for some of the course material changes if you need to update some exercises there's a new way

IT

31:49.040 --> 31:58.880

of wanting to educate about tool or something yeah

RE

I think part of this probably that making

RE

31:58.880 --> 32:09.280

it somehow flexible that maybe you can like that each exercise is not for example fixed on that

RE

32:09.280 --> 32:20.240

specific lecture that you can shuffle around the different parts of the of the content that would

RE

32:20.240 --> 32:28.160

make it easier to reuse part of it if you want to just change something but but reuse other things

RE

32:28.160 --> 32:41.280

so some kind of making it flexible to yeah to update and reuse stuff it goes to be that the

RE

32:41.280 --> 32:48.280

teacher in Copenhagen like having a similar course would want to reuse some of the exercises but but

RE

32:48.280 --> 32:55.400

maybe do some things differently okay I don't know if that would necessarily make it sustainable but

RE

32:55.400 --> 33:07.320

at least I would if the user base is two rather than one it helps a bit

IT

I think that we

IT

33:07.320 --> 33:14.960

need to consider for your adaption the adaptation of of the course over time since you've all

IT

33:14.960 --> 33:19.440

talked about that since the change from the last professor to you there's a lot of changes to how

IT

33:19.440 --> 33:24.800

you teach the course. I think they need to be considered upfront for any future

IT

33:24.800 --> 33:38.840

changes

RE

so AI for programming is possibly a thing in the future it's hard to know now I think what

RE

33:38.840 --> 33:45.440

impact it will have but it will probably have some impact in the way you program and then also in the

RE

33:45.440 --> 33:53.960

way you would teach programming it's hard to know like how to prepare for that but I guess that's

RE

33:53.960 --> 34:02.160

a factor to consider there's also the language question which is maybe a bit harder to prepare

RE

34:02.160 --> 34:12.120

for but I think still think that C is a useful language to for start to start learning and

RE

34:12.120 --> 34:22.360

programming because it and yeah it has the things that the course covers and not a lot more but

RE

34:22.360 --> 34:28.280

there are some aspects of C that it's not so nice for example scanf and printf it's not

RE

34:28.280 --> 34:38.280

the nicest way of interacting with the user so it's I mean it's not guaranteed that the course

RE

34:38.280 --> 34:43.920

will continue using C for the next 10 years for example so that would probably impact all of the

RE

34:43.920 --> 34:53.360

exercises and and most of the material as well yeah I think I can highlight possible issues I

RE

34:53.360 --> 34:56.400

don't think I have solutions for it

IT

that's also fine